

ADECO GROUP
مجموعة الدكتور علي الدهيمان

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About our CEO

Dr. Ali Bin Saleh Alduhaiman

- Faculty member - Biochemistry Department - College of Sciences - King Saud University
- PhD in Biochemistry - University of Colorado State - USA
- Title of Full Professor in 1996
- Deputy of Higher Education College in King Saud University - 1996 to 2000
- Member of several scientific commissions inside Kingdom and Abroad. Represented American Academy of Sciences and Biochemical Society in Britain
- Published several studies and researches and he has written two books about medical analysis.
- A member of the Shura Council in 2009 headed the Health and Environment Committees in the Council in that period

ADECO GROUP FOUNDED IN 2007

The office of Dr Ali Alduhaiman Environmental Consultation was established in 2007 as an individual corporation based in Riyadh , Saudi Arabia

Words from our CEO

- The measure of success for any trading companies is how they adopt the trends in market in the entire world.
- As one of the successful trading stories, ADECO is One of the prime example of integrity in its statements We are not only reacted to the changing conditions of volatile markets, but also. we excelled in finding opportunities and advantages in what others have seen as turmoil .
- ADECO's vision is to be the most admired satisfier of our customer, as partners of success. Admired not only for our high-quality products and attractive services, but also for how we react responsibly for demands that may surrounds us.
- The market way for our group & products represents exactly how the present situation is. ADECO is continuously adapting organization and resources to match the global situation and the shifting balance of the markets in which we operate.
- We take these measures from a position of financial and strategic strength, reacting to certain trends and anticipating others. The result of this continuous process is an efficient. flexible and dedicated organization.
- However, the more things change, the more some things stay the same. ADECO will always stay true to our mission: to add value to the supply chain for our products worldwide, a recipe that has proven successful for many years.
- All ADECO employees share a responsibility for how we act in relation to our customers, our consumers, our owners, our suppliers and co-workers. We, as a company. always act in a way that demonstrates that we deserve the stakeholders' confidence and appreciation.
- The ADECO Code of Conduct is a set of ethical guidelines for how we do business. It builds on ADECO's core values: Focus, Team play, Passion and Pride. The Code takes the entire value chain into consideration and provides guidance to how to live up to our reputation in practice. Therefore. all co-workers are encouraged to accept their share of our joint responsibility.
- We continuously strive to improve in the field of corporate responsibility
- Consequently, the Code of Conduct will be a document which will evolve together with our company.
- In addition to our corporate responsibility, we have a personal responsibility. We should always behave and act in a way that allows us to take pride in our achievements, our company and our trade. That, at the end of the day, is what it takes to become a successful business in the long run. To be guided by your values and take responsibility for your actions.

Ali Bin Saleh Al duhaiman

Our Identity

At ADECO, we define ourselves by the knowledge we provide. Not only we offer turnkey solutions and technology advancement, but we also dedicate our expertise to help develop our highly technical partners' skills, enhance their proficiencies, and directly contribute to customer support. Customer's support is our priority.

Our Mission

- Employing creative and competent people and working with quality suppliers
- Providing the best value and services to our customers
- Becoming an industry leader in operational efficiency, energy conversion, technology enhancer and provide environmental safety to our community for their better life.
- Focusing Our resources relevant growth sectors Of the Saudi Economy and attaining leadership status by developing scalable and profitable businesses.
- Enhancing Our employees' quality Of life.

Our vision

To excel in providing best-in-class solutions and quality services for our value growth for our stakeholders

Our values

- **People:** To attract retain, motivate highly talented employees, empower them and offer them challenging career paths in a healthy work environment .
- **Efficiency:** To allocate resources in the effective manner, avoiding wastage and achieving optimal returns.
- **Customer Focus:** To exceed customer expectations by continuously delivering to them the most relevant products and best service levels.
- **Respect & Fairness:** To deal with customers, partners, employees and authorities with the highest levels of integrity and respect, fairness in all our interactions
- **Quality;** To maintain the highest levels of quality throughout our organization, and with all external stakeholders.

Company summary

Today ADECO group qualified manpower include more than 300 ,with 180 consultants, engineers, chemists, and technicians who work in different fields like:

- 1- Environmental Studies
- 2- Scientific Sales & Maintenance
- 3- Solar & Water Technologies
- 4- Information Technology

ADECO is always happy to provide specialized and services in the field of services. Environmental development projects, sustainable energy , technology and laboratories.

Laboratory operation

ADECO is one among the top leaders in food & water laboratories operation , with a very reputation for its experience & highly qualified specialists, most of them are PhD & MSc holders.

Environmental Studies

Advisory services and environmental studies based on scientific methods. Creation of Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) system. Recognize the threats caused by insects and pests determine where the danger lays then we address the root causes of It

Scientific sales & Maintenance

Provides quality laboratory products through sales Provides highly proficient personnel for the operation of food safety and water laboratories for accurate testing results Highly experienced technical personals for the maintenance and installation of in Laboratories and other institutions in the entire kingdom.

Solar Energy

ADECO Solar specialized in implementing highly efficient and innovative solutions in Solar & Water technologies

Information Technology

Provides information technology in the following fields::

1. Geographical Information System (GIS)
2. System Integration
3. Data Storage
4. Content Management System (CMS)
5. Provides installation and LAN, WAN and other network related services

Environmental Consultation Services

Services we provide:

- Environmental Impact Assessment of Projects to meet the requirements for obtaining the necessary licenses for the establishment of these projects.
- Examples include but not limited to: Petroleum – Chemicals – Steel, Paints and Packaging Factories – Recreational Sites – Agricultural – Health Care Facilities – Residential Units – Mining & Quarry Operations – Poultry, Meat and Fishing Factories etc.
- Environmental Surveys and Studies.
- Adapting Project designs to Safe and Green Projects.
- Environmental Risks and Hazards Assessment.
- Environmental Impact Assessment Studies (EIA).
- Evaluation of environmental impact of the expansion of industrial projects.
- Environmental Records Preparation for Government Licenses
- Client assistance to fulfill PME requirements and Guidelines.
- Site surveys and assessment to determine suitability for a particular project.
- Monitoring of all three environmental media (Air, Water & Soil).
- Industrial Waste Water Analysis.
- Design of Industrial wastewater and Sewage treatment plants.
- Environmental Auditing.
- Environmental Reports of running projects.
- External audit of active environmental management system.
- Environmental Impact Assessment of the project's expansion plans.
- Disposal plans for solid and liquid wastes.

food safety hygiene

ADECO covers the field of food safety through its qualified team as Following:

- Consultations regarding hygienic conditions of food and water.
- A proper hazard identification system to determine the potential sources of diseases in food.
- Field training for deployment of environmental and health systems at the restaurants.
- Compliance of restaurants in Saudi Arabia with the regulations of General Authority for Meteorology and Environment (PME) and Saudi Ministry of Health.
- Develop solutions to reduce pollution in food production processes.

Public Health care - sanitation & pest control

Recognize the threats caused by insects and pests determine where the danger lays then we address the root causes of It
Disinfection and Sterilization for Healthcare

ISO Certification Services

We provide leading & innovative services in the areas of:

- Certifications.
- Inspection and verification.
- Outsourcing.
- Risk management.
- Technical consulting. Testing and analysis.
- Food & hospitality service.
- Training services .

ISO Services

1. ISO 9001:2015 - Quality Management System .
2. ISO/IEC 17025:2005 – General Requirement for the competence of testing and celebration laboratories .
3. OHSAS 18001:2007 – Occupational Health and Safety Management system .
4. ISO 45001:2018 - Occupational Health and Safety Management system .
5. ISO 14001:2015 - Environment Management system .
6. SA 8000:2008 – Social Accountability .

Food safety management

- 1) Codex Alimentarius – HACCP ISO 22000:2005 – Food Safety Management System .
- 2) IFS : Version 6
- 3) Global Gab : Version 5 .
- 4) RC : Version 8 - (British Retail Consortium) :
I. International BRC for food .
II. BRC-IOP for packing and Packaging.

Independent third party inspections:

- 1) BSCI – Business Social Compliance Initiative.
- 2) SEDEX – Supplier Ethical Data Exchange
- 3) NON GMO PRODUCTS – Regulation of Certification Non-Genetically Modified Products
- 4) NON GMO ANIMAL FEED – Regulation of Certification Non-Genetically Modified Feed
- 5) GOLDEN KITCHEN – Food Hygiene inspection services in Food stores.
- 6) Food Hygiene inspection services in Food store.

Training service

- 1) Accredited lead auditor, internal auditor and awareness courses for (ISO 9001, ISO 22000, ISO14001 & OHSAS 18001).
- 2) Quality system for medical devices industry (ISO 13485:2003).
- 3) Information security management system , IRCA certified.
- 4) Internal audit courses.
- 5) Hazard analysis and critical control points (HACCAP).
- 6) Cleaning and sanitation
- 7) GMP & Hygiene
- 8) Suppliers Audits
- 9) Microbiology

Scientific sales & maintenance

Laboratory operation

Service & maintenance

Laboratory instrumentation supply

Laboratory operation

- Highly experienced professional laboratory Personnel with a Bachelors Degree Holder, Masters of Science and PhD Holders to guarantee the best results of testing.
- Continuous trainings to achieve high performance.
- ISO consultation for laboratories to compete with international laboratories.
- Apply the latest technologies for sample analysis to keep you up to date.
- Consultation for new laboratory establishment starting from laboratory design, furniture, suggestion for required instruments & provide you with application notes and qualified manpower to do the job.

Business partners

Business partners

MACHERY-NAGEL products are among the world's most reliable analytical systems. They are used, for example, in industry, healthcare, biotechnology, environmental analysis and research. Numerous patents and international certifications underscore the high quality of their products and the competence of their employees.

IDEXX Water is a global provider of water testing solutions that deliver easy, rapid, accurate and cost-effective information on water quality to laboratories and public utilities around the world. IDEXX entered the water testing market in 1993 with Colilert®, now one of the most frequently used testing methods for the detection of coliforms and Escherichia coli in water worldwide. In 2012, the IDEXX Colilert®-18/Quanti-Tray® Test method became ISO standard 9308-2:2012 for detecting total coliforms and Escherichia coli in water.

EasyDisc YEA Test

EasyDisc PCA Test

EasyDisc R2A Test

Legionella pneumophila

Coliform/E. coli

Enterococci

Pseudomonas aeruginosa

Business partners

For over 35 years, INTERSCIENCE has been providing high quality equipment for microbiology, especially designed for quick and safe analyses in quality control. They offer a wide range of products, from solid sample preparation to its final bacterial enumeration, for the food and agro-food, medical, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries.

EVERmed is the medical division of the group, from which acquire the experience of over 50 years presence in the sector of the industrial and professional refrigeration, grants a highly specialized production that allow us to have always the maximum expression of the cold for every sort of application (hospitals, clinics, universities, labs, pharmacies). The company, through the collaboration of high skilled personnel, specialized in the field, offer a wide range of specific products bounding together the best possible service.

Established in 1989, we are now celebrating over 27 years of success. Centurion has grown rapidly from humble beginnings and flourished into one of the leading UK Centrifuge manufacturers. We have not forgotten our roots; with the support and success Of our business partners (worldwide distributors) we have become a force to be reckoned with competing against larger multi nationals. We have done this by simply continuing our ethos of offering competitive, good quality products and offering superb customer care.

Business partners

3M Science.
Applied to Life.™

3M is a leader of innovative solutions that help the **food** and beverage industries optimize the quality of their products to enable consumer protection.

Business partners

BICASA
We Lead Lab

World leader in the field of lab furniture with a wide range of solutions The most comprehensive range of product lines on the market Technical furniture lines designed to keep pace with C4 technological innovation in analytical and laboratory instrumentation Each product represents the synthesis of experience gained in over 70 years of history

Modularity and flexibility are the basis of each product Materials, finishes and colors guarantee the perfect integration of the different product lines for an organic and efficient design of every type of laboratory.

NOVISPHERE

NoviSphere™ PE 254 is a cost-effective, high-performance UV pathogen eradication unit that can either establish a new rarified environment or re-establish an existing one. The product integrates components and purification technologies based on proven scientific methods that eliminate biohazardous viral and bacteriological material and other airborne contaminants from enclosed spaces of any size. NoviSphere™ PE 254 operates continuously to remove airborne pathogens from the environment, greatly reducing contamination and risk of infection.

 evoqua
WATER TECHNOLOGIES

Evoqua Water Technologies is a leading provider of water and wastewater treatment solutions, offering a broad portfolio of products, services and expertise to support industrial, municipal and recreational customers.

Laboratory instrumentation supply

Service & maintenance

If you are facing problems with your instruments and of you need complete maintenance solution ADECOR has highly qualified engineer to solve your service and maintenance problems

Highly experienced services for high performance devices to suit aspirations

We seek to provide maintenance and technical support services that befit our customers and advance our precious country

Services we provide:

- Time based "TBM" & Condition based maintenance "CBM"
- Maintenance & Spare parts
- Services Contracts
- Equipment Calibration
- Technical Support & Training

From Repair-focused to Reliability-focused

Solar energy

ADECOSOLAR specialized in implementing highly efficient and innovative solutions in Solar Water Technologies.

ADECOSOLAR has two main lines of business:

- Highly diversified Solar Energy Solutions.
- Water Technologies Solutions for desalination and reuse In the Renewable Energy sector, ADECOSOLAR's main focus is on harnessing the abundantly available and free energy from the sun.

OUR VISION

ADECOSOLAR leader company in the area of environmental and renewable energy consultations and implementations, offering the best scientific and technological solutions, and maintaining optimum professional performance.

ADECOSOLAR quality control programs and its management strive always to guarantee top quality and accuracy using the latest technological solutions.

OUR MISSION

Act responsibly: Enabling a sustainable future by accelerating the adaptation of solar technology.

Drive innovation: Innovation and quality are key characteristics of our product and solar solutions.

Be customer friendly and reliable: Flexible and customized high — tech PV solutions and reliable support to fit your specific needs.

- More than 30,000,000 S.R Investments
- More than 3 MW Pipeline in 2017
- More than 15 Projects completed around the Kingdom.

Solar lighting

Solar PV power generation for telecom tower of mobile operation

Solar car parking

Solar water desalination reserves osmosis

Information technology

Our services

ADECO present many services in the information technology field, including:

Geographic Information systems (GIS)

Data storage

Employment

Web Portals development

Networks

Devolving Web Portals and Electronic Services

Content Management system (CMS)

System Integration

Maintenance and Technical Support

Supplying and Installation

Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

ADECO has experience in Information Systems, such that

- It develops application and systems for Geographic Information.
- It implements the smart solution and applies it to the Geographic Information Systems.

Data storage

We at ADECO realize that information is the most important factor for clients, and for securing the information and clients' data there must be a plan to store them in an efficient and complete manner. Store the information and data either by having a backup copy, a copy of the original, primary storage, through the infrastructure as a service, or cloud backup. ADECO will help its clients on designing and implementing a strategy to store the data and the backup copies to improve clients' systems and reduce the total cost

Employment

ADECO provides the best-qualified people in every aspect of the information technology like

- Network engineers and technicians.
- Database programmers and supervisors.
- Information security specialists

Web Portals development

The blooming of IT and the digital revolution that taking place in the world in general and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in particular (Vision 2030), the transaction to the electronic government, and the unprecedented turnout on electronic transactions and e-commerce, web portals became dynamic, effective, and an indispensable tool in the market Also, government agencies providing continuous and great service for citizens because they were affected positively in raising the efficiency of the performance of these movement agencies and effectiveness in handling. In addition, the reduction of time and effort on citizens, and the potentials it holds in the vast amount of information exchange the world is witnessing today.

Networks

ADECO presents different solution for different computer networks (wired or wireless)

Devolving web Portals and Electronic Services

We understand and analyses the requested services and through a specialized team that serve the beneficiary and working to limit the services. And then determine the course of the services transactions procedures and then do the work of electronic forms and then develop e-services with the internal regulations of the organization and submit them to the beneficiary in a respectful and professional manner, with all necessary explanations and in different formats (Flash-Video - writing).

content Management system (CMS)

We see that presenting the content in a professional, effective, and attractive manner increase the success of the website and the web portal. So ADECO will develop a CMS to the clients since we excel greatly in this field because of the ideas, innovation, and experience of our team. Just deliver your folders and we transform them with ease to your website, with it a collection of completed services to manage the content to edit or add content easily. Also, we strengthen the system with mechanisms that help the website to spread so it will be compatible with the Search Engine Optimization (SEO).

System Integration

The IT team starts to study and understand the client's requirements and needs until they have a clear vision of the ideal mechanism to be applied to connect the existing client's systems in an integrated manner to achieve the client's goals. This will be implemented with new techniques used to connect systems or develop a software specially designed to connect systems together, or the use of preexisting programs that connect systems and check its integration together.

Maintenance and Technical support

ADECO provide support and maintenance services, and that can be done with a special contract. ADECO signed many contracts which led us to excel in this field too. The contract starts from the time it is signed for the safety of the product and monitor the quality of performance. We offer the service either by e-mail or phone call in addition to the possibility of providing the service using the latest technologies in remote login Remote Access, where the engineer diagnoses the problem and contribute to solving them with the client.

Supplying and Installation

- ADECO supply, install, and maintain the following:
- Hardware, software.
- Laptop and personal computers (PC).
- Different kinds of servers.
- Printers and scanners.
- Computer parts and accessories.
- Time Attendance and Leave Management System devices and RFID devices.
- Smart Boards.
- and everything needed in the field-

Activities in pictures

Experiences

شركة المياه الوطنية
National Water Company

Water and waste water plants and laboratories under ADECO supervision central region area (Riyadh and nearby areas)

- Riyadh Water Laboratory
- Al Kharj Water Laboratory & Sewage Treatment Plant
- Howtat Bani Tamim Water Laboratory
- Al Hariq Water Laboratory
- Aflaj Water Laboratory
- Wadl Ad-Dawasir Laboratory & Sewage Treatment Plant
- As Sulayyil Water Laboratory
- Durmah Water Laboratory
- Al Muzahimiyah Water Laboratory
- Al Quwaiyah Water Laboratory
- Shaqra Water Laboratory & Sewage Treatment Plant
- Al Ghat Water Laboratory & Sewage Treatment Plant .
- Al Majmaah Water Laboratory & Sewage Treatment Plant
- Rumah Water Laboratory
- Afif Water Laboratory & Sewage Treatment Plant
- Al Dawadmi Water Laboratory.
- Dir'yah Water Laboratory .
- Zulfi Water Laboratory & Sewage Treatment Plant
- Thadiq Water Laboratory
- Hurayimla Water Laboratory

- Providing laboratory instrument , tools an chemicals for National water company laboratory.

South Region (Jizan- AL-Baha -Najran)

- AL-Baha Water Directorate central laboratory
- Jizan water & Jizan sewage treatment plant
- Najran water Laboratory

Eastern Region (Dammam-Khobar Zahran-Jubail-Hafr Albatin- Ahsaa - Khafgy)

- LABORATORY ANALYSIS OF SAMPLES FOR WATER AND STP

Makkah AlMukaramah Region

- Makkah water LABORATORY
- ANALYSIS OF SAMPLES FOR WATER

Experiences

وزارة الشؤون
البلدية والقروية
Ministry of Municipal & Rural Affairs

Ministry of municipal and rural affair

- Studying and Observation of Public Health's Pests.
- Studying of the Electronic Health Control.
- Observation of hormones and antibiotics residues in meat and poultry and their products.
- Studying and Observation of additives and heavy metals in food, beverages and juices.
- Monitoring and Detection of Salmonella in poultry and poultry products.
- Monitoring and Detection of pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables and some food commodities

Ministry of Interior

- Maintenance of forensic laboratories of general department of criminal evidence and their sub directorate
- Riyadh
- Qassim
- Dammam
- Jeddah
- Abha
- Hail
- Makkah
- Madinah
- Jazan
- Najran
- Tabuk
- Qurayyat
- Al jouf
- Arar
- Deerah
- Albaha
- Taif
- Supplying, installation and operation for solar street lights to light up 3 KM road at ABHA city , Aseer Region , Saudi Arabia

وزارة البيئة والمياه والزراعة
Ministry of Environment Water & Agriculture
Kingdom of Saudi Arabia المملكة العربية السعودية

- Operation and maintenance laboratories of the Organic Agriculture Center in Qassim .
- Providing laboratory instrument and tools for fish safety laboratory.
- Providing laboratory instrument , tools an chemicals for pesticide residual laboratory.

وزارة التعليم
Ministry of Education

Ministry of Education

- Maintenance of prince Sultan center for special education support services in Riyadh

Experiences

Al-Qassim Municipality

- Operation and maintenance of food safety laboratory.

Eastern region Municipality

- Operation and maintenance of food safety laboratory
- Monitoring of dangerous industrial activities

Jeddah Municipality

- Supervising the work of hygiene in the city.
- Operation and maintenance of food safety laboratory.

Hail Municipality

- Supervision of hygiene and environmental health and environmental sanitation.
- Operation and maintenance of food safety laboratory

Experiences

Unaizah Municipality

- Applying health regulation for the stores and shops related to the effect on the public health.
- Operation and maintenance of Unaizah municipality.

Al Rass Municipality

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools for food safety laboratory
- Operation and maintenance of food safety laboratory.

Al Kharj Municipality

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools for food safety laboratory

King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals

- Operation and maintenance of university laboratory

Assir Municipality

- Operation and maintenance of food safety laboratory
- Improvement of landfill in Abha
- IT project for Data storage Archiving investment contracts

SWCC

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools

Experiences

Khamis Mushaut Municipality

- Operation and maintenance of food safety laboratory.
- Public health pests control in urban.

SFDA

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools .

Al Qassim University

- Operation and maintenance of educational factory for faculty of agriculture and veterinary medicine .
- Operation and maintenance of veterinary clinic of faculty of agriculture and veterinary medicine .
- Maintenance of all scientific instruments at the faculty of applied science .

المؤسسة العامة للتدريب التقني والمهني
Technical and Vocational Training Corporation

TVTC

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools .

Experiences

سيماكو الدوائية
SPIMACO ADDWAEIH

Spimaco Addwaeih

- Providing and installation furniture of laboratory.

King Saud University

- maintenance of all scientific instruments at the laboratory of college of science in biochemistry
- Maintenance and calibration of scientific instrument .

Taif University

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools for faculty of sciences
- maintenance of scientific instruments at the laboratory of college of science in biochemistry

Tatweer education holding co.

- maintenance of Tatweer education Holding co.

King Khalid University

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools.

الهيئة السعودية للمواصفات والمقاييس والجودة
Saudi Standards, Metrology and Quality Org.

SASO

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools.
- Maintenance and calibration some of scientific instrument .

Experiences

Um Elqura University

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools

مستشفى الملك فيصل التخصصي ومركز الأبحاث
King Faisal Specialist Hospital & Research Centre
مؤسسة عامة - Gen. Org.

KFSH&RC

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools.
- maintenance of some instruments at the laboratory

جامعة حائل
University of Ha'il

Hail University

- Providing and installation of laboratory furniture for the Faculty of Medicine

جامعة الأمير سطام بن عبد العزيز
Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University

Prince Sattam University

- Maintenance of all scientific instruments at the central laboratory.
- Providing laboratory instrument and tools & installation of laboratory furniture & Operating University central laboratory

Tabuk Municipality

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools for food safety laboratory.

King Abdul Aziz University

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools

Experiences

KFU
جامعة الملك فيصل
KING FAISAL UNIVERSITY
جامعة ووطن.. نماء.. واستدامة..

King Faisal University

- Project in solar for 3500 units of solar power street lighting system.
- Solar foot bridge project.
- Off-grid solar power system for waiting area building project.
- Solar heating system for Olympic pool project.
- Solar water heating system of male and female building project.
- Solar water heating system for KFU stadium.
- Al-Shamalley 12 solar water heating system project.
- Environmental impact assessment studies for the university city for students

المؤسسة العامة للحبوب
Saudi Grains Organization (SAGO)
المملكة العربية السعودية

SAGO

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools

Ministry of National Guard

- Providing laboratory instrument and tools

Duba Municipality

- Improvement of landfill

أمانة الطائف
TAIF MUNICIPALITY

TAIF Municipality

- Environmental impact assessment studies for the university city for RANYAH landfill

Experiences

some of Our clients in environmental consultations
& environmental impact assessment studies

أسترا للتعدين
ASTRA MINING

Experiences

REDANATIONAL

شركة مصنع عسق للبلاستيك
ASG

أسيا للبلاستيك والتغليف
ASIA PLASTIC & PACKAGING

مجموعة شركات موجة
MOJAH GROUP COMPANIES